

The Role of Industrial Zones for Economic Development in the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus

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Abstract

Mahmut Kanber, representing the Cyprus Turkish Chamber of Tradesmen and Craftsmen Organizations and Unions, asserts that industrial zones are crucial for securing the economic autonomy of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus. Kanber asserts that they have faced prolonged challenges in attracting foreign investment and safeguarding local producers, highlighting the need of industrial zones to bolster Turkish Cypriot tradesmen, artisans, industrialists, merchants, and small producers. These zones are crucial for enhancing industrial capacity, augmenting modern and high value-added manufacturing, promoting exports, and facilitating access to new markets. Kanber asserts that industrial zones might serve as an economic growth paradigm for the Turkish Cypriot population, although this potential remains mostly untapped. He asserts that rather than implementing strategies to enhance production capacity, bolster the local economy, and cultivate a modern industrial culture, the focus is on enticing foreign investment to the nation under favorable circumstances (CEYHAN, 2020). Kanber further asserts that this strategy signifies a deficiency in economic foresight and a lack of confidence in domestic manufacturers. (Akçay & Saygili, 2019) The Turkish Cypriot populace recognizes the constrained nature of the island's economy, the absence of strategic planning to enhance local capacity in managing industrial zones, and the deficiency of requisite infrastructure for small and medium-sized enterprises to collaborate, form cooperatives, and engage in export production, thereby corroborating Kanber's apprehensions (CEYHAN, 2020). Kanber asserts that prioritizing the attraction of foreign capital under favorable conditions, rather than implementing policies to enhance production capacity, bolster the local economy, and foster a modern industrial paradigm, reflects a deficiency in economic vision and a lack of confidence in domestic producers.

Keywords : TRNC, Northern Cyprus Industry, TRNC and Developed Regions, Development in TRNC, TRNC and Industrialization

Introduction

Kanber asserts that industrial zones had the ability to serve as an economic growth model for the Turkish Cypriot population, although this potential remains mostly untapped. Global industrialization activities are associated with challenges pertaining to urbanization and environmental degradation. Consequently, it is essential to establish industrial zones in a systematic and organized manner (CEYHAN, 2020). The beneficial impact of regional economic groups for Turkey's exports is evident. Given the constrained economic framework of the Turkish Cypriot population, it is evident that industrial zones may significantly enhance economic autonomy by bolstering local businesses and augmenting their exports. (Yalman & Zorlutuna, 2021) (Akçay & Saygili, 2019) (DEMİR, 2020) (CEYHAN, 2020) The establishment of industrial zones, enhancement of production capacity, promotion of high value-added manufacturing, and facilitation of exports represent significant opportunities for the economic advancement of the Turkish Cypriot population. The significance and potential of industrial zones for economic growth are crucial in assisting local producers, enhancing production capacity, promoting exports, and facilitating access to new markets (CEYHAN, 2020) (Yalman & Zorlutuna, 2021). The development of essential infrastructure enabling small and medium-sized firms to congregate in industrial zones, create cooperatives, and engage in export production is crucial for bolstering the local economy.

Aim

The establishment of industrial zones is crucial for the economic autonomy of the Turkish Cypriot population. The role of industrial zones in enhancing production capacity, facilitating contemporary and high value-added manufacturing, promoting exports, and accessing new markets is indisputable. Facilitating local businesses and small producers, while maintaining strategic planning and cooperation in the administration of industrial zones, is essential for the sustained growth of the Turkish Cypriot economy. According to Kanber, political will is focused on implementing policies that provide immediate solutions rather than articulating a long-term goal to enhance local manufacturing capability. The significance of industrial zones in securing the economic autonomy of the Turkish Cypriot population must not be overlooked, and this potential warrants assessment.

The Relationship Between Social Capital and Trust

The notions of social capital and trust significantly contribute to economic growth. A strong degree of trust in establishing shared societal objectives for the future also promotes economic growth within that community. The enhancement and reinforcement of collaboration and collaborative efforts, facilitated by social relationships and the proliferation of educational possibilities, are economic advantages of social capital. Consequently, the adoption and execution of methods to enhance local production capacity in the development of industrial zones is crucial for fortifying social capital and trust ties. The Turkish Cypriot populace recognizes the constrained nature of the island's economy. The absence of strategic planning to enhance local competence in managing industrial zones, coupled with inadequate infrastructure for small and medium-sized firms to form clusters, establish cooperatives, and engage in export-oriented manufacturing, substantiates Kanber's apprehensions. (CEYHAN, 2020) (DEMİR, 2020). Mahmut Kanber believes that industrial zones are fundamental to economic autonomy and development in the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus. Kanber asserts that industrial zones must be used efficiently to bolster local output, enhance exports, and establish a contemporary industrial framework. (Yalman & Zorlutuna, 2021) (CEYHAN, 2020)

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Nonetheless, despite the constrained economic realities of the Turkish Cypriot minority, he highlights the absence of policies and planning focused on enhancing local capacity for the administration of industrial zones. Consequently, it is underscored that industrial zones are pivotal in securing the economic autonomy and advancement of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus. Kanber asserts that there is an absence of strategic planning in the administration of industrial zones intended to enhance local capacity. In an environment lacking the requisite infrastructure for small and medium-sized firms to cluster, form cooperatives, and engage in export-oriented manufacturing, foreign capital is anticipated to bridge this gap. This condition exacerbates the decrease of local production capability and drives small producers into extinction. Organized Industrial Zones not only facilitate systematic industrialization but also provide economic advantages, including cost reduction, the establishment of modern infrastructure, and the mitigation of regional developmental disparities (CEYHAN, 2020). The aggregation of small and medium-sized firms facilitates the realization of economic economies of scale and enhances production (KAVAKCI & Görmüş, 2018).

Methodology

The enhancement of social capital is a significant outcome of industrial zones. Trust and collaboration among enterprises facilitate cost reduction, the exchange of innovative technologies and information, and the enhancement of collective action and learning possibilities. Consequently, it may provide favorable economic outcomes, including enhanced production capacity, elevated exports, and regional growth (KAVAKCI & Görmüş, 2018). Consequently, it can be said that industrial zones are pivotal in securing the economic autonomy and sustained growth of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus. Nonetheless, the absence of policies and strategic planning to enhance local competence in the administration and development of industrial zones, as noted by Kanber, may impede the achievement of economic independence. (Akçay & Saygılı, 2019) (CEYHAN, 2020; KAVAKCI & Görmüş, 2018) (ÇAPAR & Yayla, 2019)

A thorough strategic planning and management framework must be implemented for industrial zones to enhance the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises in the region, foster

production development, and augment export capacity (Yalman & Zorlutuna, 2021) (KAVAKCI & Görmüş, 2018) (CEYHAN, 2020).

Management of Industrial Zones and Empowerment of Local Producers

Kanber asserts that there is an absence of strategic planning focused on enhancing local capacity for the administration of industrial zones. Stating that the necessary infrastructure has not been created for small and medium-sized enterprises to cluster, become cooperatives and carry out export-oriented production, Kanber emphasizes that instead, foreign capital is expected to fill this gap.

Nonetheless, regarding regional development, it is crucial to enhance and assist local producers in the administration of industrial zones. Kavakcı and Görmüş, 2018 Kanber contends that this circumstance exacerbates the deterioration of local production capacity and drives small producers into extinction.

Effective and efficient administration of industrial zones necessitates the support of clustering and cooperative structures established by small and medium-sized firms, alongside the development of policies and practices to enhance export-oriented production capacity.

Economic Independence and Industrial Zones

The significant function of industrial zones in fostering economic independence and growth is undeniable. Mahmut Kanber said that industrial zones need to serve as the foundational element of the economic growth strategy for the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus. Kanber says that the present approach signifies a deficiency in economic foresight and a lack of confidence in local producers. The objective is to entice foreign investment to the nation under favorable circumstances; however, measures that enhance production capacity, fortify the local economy, and establish a contemporary industrial framework are overlooked.

Literature Review

Literature on regional development suggests that industrialization and industrial zones are essential for economic autonomy and sustained growth. It is acknowledged that the administration and development of industrial zones in the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus lack sufficient strategy and planning to bolster local manufacturers and small enterprises. Kanber asserts that, rather than proposing a long-term vision to enhance local capability, political will is characterized by short-term initiatives designed to address immediate concerns. This strategy is seen as a sign of insufficient economic foresight and skepticism towards local producers. To guarantee the economic autonomy and sustained advancement of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus, a holistic strategy and planning methodology must be used to bolster local producers and small enterprises in the administration and development of industrial zones. (CEYHAN, 2020) (ÇAPAR & Yayla, 2019) (Kavakci & Görmüş, 2018) (Akçay & Saygili, 2019) A systematic and strategic approach must be formulated to enhance local production capabilities, assist small and medium-sized firms, and promote export-oriented manufacturing. Conversely, emphasizing the allure of foreign investment under favorable circumstances may exacerbate the deterioration of local production capacity and lead to the extinction of small enterprises. To guarantee the economic autonomy and sustained progress of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus, thorough planning is essential to bolster local producers and small enterprises in the administration and advancement of industrial zones. A deliberate strategy aimed at enhancing local capability should be implemented. Essential infrastructure must be developed to facilitate the clustering of small and medium-sized enterprises, enabling them to form cooperatives and engage in export-oriented manufacturing. The emphasis should be on enhancing local manufacturing capacity rather than relying on foreign capital to address this imbalance. (CEYHAN, 2020) (Demirbaş et al., 2020) Kanber, an advocate for the significance of industrial zones in the economic advancement of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus, asserts that political will must establish a long-term vision to enhance local capacity; otherwise, local production will be entirely incapacitated if industrial zones are transferred to foreign capital (CEYHAN, 2020). Kanber asserts that the Turkish Cypriot populace is cognizant of the constrained framework of the island's economy, and that any initiative directed towards enhancing local ability in the administration of industrial zones He asserts that

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no strategic planning has been conducted and that the necessary infrastructure for small and medium-sized firms to cluster, form cooperatives, and engage in export-oriented manufacturing has not been established. He asserts that foreign capital was anticipated to bridge this gap; nevertheless, this resulted in a further fall of local production capacity and led to the elimination of small producers (Demirbaş et al., 2020). Research on interregional income inequality in Turkey elucidates disparities in development via the establishment of growth poles by foreign economies in locations characterized by substantial market possibilities, influenced by capital, skilled labor, and population density (ÇAPAR & Yayla, 2019). In the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus, prioritizing the attraction of foreign capital under favorable conditions may adversely impact local production capacity due to the absence of a strategic plan to bolster local producers (ÇAPAR & Yayla, 2019) (CEYHAN, 2020). The emphasis on recruiting foreign capital under favorable circumstances exacerbates the erosion of local production capacity and threatens the survival of small firms. In this context, it contends that political will should promote a long-term vision to enhance local capacity rather than implement short-term initiatives. Industrial zones are crucial for enhancing production capacity, fostering contemporary and high value-added manufacturing, promoting exports, and facilitating access to new markets. Kanber asserts that these zones should be established to bolster Turkish Cypriot traders, artisans, manufacturers, merchants, and small producers. (CEYHAN, 2020) Kanber asserts that industrial zones have to be used to enhance contemporary, high value-added industry. Industrial zones are seen crucial for promoting exports and facilitating access to new markets. Kanber emphasizes that industrial zones are crucial for enabling the Turkish Cypriot population to access new markets. Industrial zones are proposed to bolster Turkish Cypriot traders, artisans, industrialists, merchants, and small manufacturers.

Findings

The Turkish Cypriot Chamber of Tradesmen and Craftsmen and Mahmut Kanber assert that industrial zones might serve as a viable economic growth model for the Turkish Cypriot population, although they underscore that this potential is being squandered. Kanber critiques that rather than implementing measures to enhance production capacity, bolster the local economy, and

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establish a modern industrial framework, the focus is placed on enticing foreign investment under favorable circumstances. Kanber argues that prioritizing the attraction of foreign capital signifies a deficiency in economic foresight and a lack of confidence in domestic producers. The research highlights that the notion of trust enhances economic growth via social capital, underscoring the significance of industrial zones in bolstering local manufacturers (KAVAKCI & Görmüş, 2018). Conversely, it is said that the goals of OIZs include industrial growth, the establishment of consistent infrastructure, and the mitigation of regional developmental disparities. Kanber believes that measures aimed at enhancing production capacity, fortifying the local economy, and fostering a modern industrial paradigm should be implemented. Kanber contends that prioritizing the attraction of foreign capital under favorable circumstances signifies a deficiency in economic foresight and a lack of confidence in domestic producers. In conclusion, Mahmut Kanber asserts that industrial zones might significantly contribute to the economic advancement of the Turkish Cypriot population; nevertheless, this potential remains unexploited, and prioritizing foreign investment may yield adverse effects. Kanber believes that measures aimed at enhancing production capacity, fortifying the local economy, and fostering a modern industrial paradigm should be implemented. Kanber contends that the emphasis on recruiting foreign capital under favorable circumstances signifies a deficiency in economic foresight and a lack of confidence in domestic producers. He asserts that a long-term economic vision, rather than political will, should be proposed to enhance local capability. If industrial zones are transferred to foreign capital, indigenous industry might be entirely incapacitated. In conclusion, Kanber asserts that industrial zones may significantly contribute to the economic growth of the Turkish Cypriot population; nevertheless, this potential remains untapped, and prioritizing foreign capital would have adverse effects.

Creating the Economic Vision

In opposition to Kanber's perspective, it might be said that the attraction of foreign money to the nation is as significant. In the short term, foreign capital inflows may stimulate economic development and employment (Yalman & Zorlutuna, 2021). Moreover, the transfer of technology and expertise facilitated by foreign investments may enhance the efficiency and competitiveness

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of domestic enterprises (may & Koç, 2019). Conversely, foreign investment may be essential for the creation and maintenance of industrial zones (CEYHAN, 2020). In this situation, political will must cultivate a vision and strategy that enhances local capability while simultaneously rendering international investments appealing. Beyond its immediate economic benefits, foreign capital plays a crucial role in enhancing the competitiveness of domestic enterprises and fostering long-term export development. (Yalman & Zorlutuna, 2021; Can & Koç, 2019) (CEYHAN, 2020) Kanber asserts that the political will emphasizes the allure of foreign investment under favorable circumstances, leading to a reduction in local production capacity and the demise of small enterprises. Conversely, research indicating that trust within the framework of social capital promotes economic growth implies a long-term economic perspective and supports legislative initiatives for local producers and entrepreneurs. (Yalman & Zorlutuna, 2021; Kavakci & Görmüş, 2018). Enhancing small and medium-sized firms, augmenting production capacity, facilitating export-oriented manufacturing, and accessing new markets will expedite the economic development of the Turkish minority in Cyprus.

Argument

Kanber said that no strategic planning to enhance local capacity was used in the administration of industrial zones, resulting in the clustering of small and medium-sized firms and the formation of cooperatives. He contends that the requisite infrastructure has not been developed for the industrial zones to enhance productivity and facilitate export-oriented manufacturing, and that confidence in local manufacturers should be bolstered. Kanber asserts that no strategic planning has been used in the administration of industrial zones to enhance local capability. Kanber asserts that the requisite infrastructure for small and medium-sized enterprises to form clusters, establish cooperatives, and engage in export-oriented production is lacking, resulting in a further decline in local production capacity and threatening the survival of small producers. Mahmut Kanber, representing the Chamber of Turkish Cypriot Tradesmen and Craftsmen, asserts that industrial zones may significantly contribute to the economic advancement of the Turkish Cypriot population; yet, this potential remains untapped. Kanber critiques the emphasis placed on enticing foreign investment under favorable circumstances, stating that this reflects a deficiency in

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economic foresight and a lack of confidence in domestic producers. Kanber asserts that measures aimed at enhancing production capacity, fortifying the local economy, and establishing a contemporary industrial framework should be implemented. He asserts that a long-term economic vision, rather than political will, should be proposed to enhance local capability. Otherwise, indigenous manufacturing may be entirely undermined if industrial zones are transferred to foreign investment. Consequently, it is said that industrial zones provide significant potential for the economic advancement of the Turkish Cypriot population; nevertheless, this potential remains unexploited, necessitating the formulation of a long-term economic strategy for local manufacturers and entrepreneurs (KAVAKCI & Görmüş, 2018). (Yalman & Zorlutuna, 2021; Ceyhan, 2020). He asserts that policies aimed at enhancing production capacity, fortifying the local economy, and cultivating a modern industrial comprehension should be implemented, contending that foreign capital-centric policies signify a deficiency in economic foresight and a lack of confidence in domestic producers. In conclusion, the Turkish Cypriot Chamber of Tradesmen and Craftsmen and Mahmut Kanber assert that political will must cultivate a sustainable economic vision and supportive policies for local manufacturers and businesses. To secure economic growth, it is crucial to bolster small and medium-sized firms, enhance production capacity, encourage export-oriented manufacturing, and access new markets. Likewise, the source (CEYHAN, 2020) underscores that structured industrial zones contribute to the development of industrial regions by their uncontrolled proliferation in urban centers.

Supporting SMEs

The study "The Effects of KOSGEB Supports on Export and Regional Development in the TR 72 Region" asserts that entrepreneurial activities are crucial for economic growth and development, thus emphasizing the need to support small and medium-sized enterprises (Yalman & Zorlutuna, 2021). Kanber's perspectives underscore the significance of small producers and SMEs in economic growth, asserting that political will must foster long-term policies in this context. defends his rectitude.

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The research entitled The Concept of Trust in the Context of Social Capital underscores that elevated levels of social capital and trust promote economic growth. In this environment, Kanber's perspectives on the need of enhancing confidence in local producers and businesses are becoming more significant.

Mahmut Kanber, representing the Turkish Cypriot Chamber of Tradesmen and Craftsmen, asserts that industrial zones could significantly contribute to the economic advancement of the Turkish Cypriot community; however, this potential remains underexploited, and prioritizing foreign investment may yield detrimental effects. Kanber asserts that political will must cultivate a long-term economic vision to enhance local competence. He underscores that strategic planning must focus on bolstering small and medium-sized firms, enhancing production capacity, facilitating export-oriented manufacturing, and expanding into new markets. The construction of essential infrastructure enabling small and medium-sized firms to cluster, form cooperatives, and engage in export-oriented manufacturing is becoming significant (Yalman & Zorlutuna, 2021). The research on the Concept of Trust within Social Capital highlights the beneficial impact of social capital on economic growth, including its religious, social, and economic dimensions. In this environment, it is essential to formulate a strategy plan focused on enhancing local capacity for the administration of industrial zones, supporting SMEs, and fostering trust-based partnerships. The Presidency of the Turkish Cypriot Chamber of Tradesmen and Craftsmen, together with Mahmut Kanber, contends that industrial zones might significantly contribute to the economic advancement of the Turkish Cypriot population; however, this potential has not been well assessed. Kanber asserts that rather than enticing foreign investment under favorable circumstances, measures should be implemented that enhance production capacity, fortify the local economy, and establish a modern industrial framework. The impact of customer happiness, trust, and cost factors on company performance: The Turkish Cypriot population recognizes the constrained nature of the island's economy. Kanber asserts that there has been no strategic planning to enhance local capacity in the administration of industrial zones, highlighting the absence of essential infrastructure for small and medium-sized enterprises to cluster, form cooperatives, and engage in export production. Kanber believes that political will must prioritize a long-term goal to enhance local capability instead of implementing short-term initiatives.

Supporting Small and Medium Enterprises

Kanber asserts that the necessary infrastructure for small and medium-sized firms to cluster, form cooperatives, and engage in export production has yet to be developed in industrial zones. Furthermore, the cited source underscores that entrepreneurial endeavors, often associated with small and medium-sized enterprises, significantly contribute to the national economy. In summary, sources that endorse Kanber's perspectives suggest that industrial zones may significantly contribute to the economic growth of the Turkish Cypriot population, enhance local production capacity, and foster a contemporary industrial paradigm. Kanber asserts that the lack of adequate infrastructure in industrial zones prevents small and medium-sized firms from forming cooperatives and engaging in export production. The cited source highlights the enabling impact of globalization via market development and the enhancement of knowledge in productive advertising and marketing services within the framework of economic globalization. Mahmut Kanber's perspectives, in conjunction with the Cyprus Turkish Tradesmen and Craftsmen Chamber, indicate that industrial zones might play a pivotal role in the economic advancement of the Turkish Cypriot population; nevertheless, this potential is inadequately harnessed. Kanber contends that measures aimed at enhancing production capacity, fortifying the local economy, and fostering a contemporary industrial paradigm should be implemented.

Creating the Economic Vision

President Mahmut Kanber believes that political will is essential for formulating a long-term, strategic economic strategy aimed at enhancing indigenous manufacturing capability. The numbered sources highlight that elevated levels of social capital and trust promote economic growth. Research supporting Kanber's perspectives indicates that industrial zones may significantly contribute to the economic advancement of the Turkish Cypriot people, enhance local production capabilities, and foster a modern industrial paradigm. In the administration of industrial

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zones, fostering confidence in local manufacturers and entrepreneurs, supporting SMEs, and executing strategic planning are crucial for economic growth.

Protecting Local Production Capacity

Kanber contends that the allure of foreign investment under favorable circumstances has exacerbated the decrease of local production capacity and led to the extinction of small enterprises. The cited source underscores that inadequate planning during the establishment of structured industrial zones has resulted in the scattering of industrial regions inside metropolitan centers. Consequently, Kanber's perspectives and the data from the sources indicate that the management and strategic planning of industrial zones need reorganization to enhance local production capacity and cultivate a modern industrial paradigm. Kanber underscores the need of political will to articulate a long-term strategy for enhancing local capacity, while the cited source highlights that social capital promotes economic growth. In this context, enhancing local capacity for industrial zone administration, supporting SMEs, and fostering trust-based partnerships are key components. It is essential to implement these measures to unlock the economic growth potential of the Turkish Cypriot population.

Conclusion

Mahmut Kanber, representing the Turkish Cypriot Chamber of Tradesmen and Craftsmen, asserts that political will must establish a long-term economic vision and plan to enhance local capabilities. The cited source emphasizes that social capital promotes economic growth. Kanber contends that industrial zones may significantly contribute to the economic advancement of the Turkish Cypriot population; however, this potential has not been adequately harnessed. He asserts that measures aimed at enhancing production capacity, fortifying the local economy, and cultivating a modern industrial paradigm should be implemented. In the administration of industrial zones, increasing confidence in local producers and entrepreneurs, assisting small and medium-sized enterprises, and engaging in strategic planning are crucial for economic growth.

Nonetheless, some counter-arguments may also be articulated. Concentrating only on enhancing local producer capacity in the administration of industrial zones may overlook the nation's wider economic interests. Attracting foreign investment under favorable circumstances might also promote economic growth. Moreover, excessive assistance for SMEs may hinder substantial investments. Although cultivating trust-based relationships is essential, prioritizing a professional management strategy may also be necessary. Consequently, it may be more suitable to implement a balanced strategy in the administration of industrial zones, which will enhance local production capabilities and provide a competitive edge to the nation in the global arena.

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